

Viscosity of Uranyl Soaps

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The viscosity results of uranyl soaps in dimethylformamide have been explained satisfactorily in terms of the equations proposed by Einstein, Vand, Mouluk and Jones-Dole. The values of the CMC and molar volume of uranyl soaps calculated from these equations are in close agreement.

THE most striking feature of metal soaps has been their increasing importance in industries. Although considerable work has been done on alkali, alkaline and transition metal soaps, little is known about rare earth metal soaps¹⁻⁶. Kapoor and Bhandari⁶ reported the preparation of uranium(IV) and dioxo-uranium(VI) soaps. In our previous communication⁷ conductivity behaviour of uranyl soaps in dimethylformamide was studied. The present work deals with the study of viscosity of uranyl soap solutions in dimethylformamide in order to examine their micellar behaviour and to see the validity of various known equations.

required amount of aqueous solution of uranyl nitrate with constant stirring. The soaps were filtered off, washed with distilled water and ethanol, first dried in an air-oven at 50° and then under reduced pressure at room temperature. The soaps were purified and analysed. The reproducibility of the results was checked by preparing two samples of the soap under similar conditions.

The viscosity and density of the solutions of uranyl soaps were measured by Ostwald's viscometer and pyknometer. All measurements were made at 40±0.05°.

Experimental

Caprylic, capric and uranyl nitrate (all B. D. H.) were used for the preparation of uranyl soaps. Uranyl soaps were prepared by direct metathesis of the corresponding potassium soaps with the

Results and Discussion

Density: The density (*d*) of the solutions of uranyl soaps (caprylate and caprate) in DMF increases at first rapidly and then slowly with the increase in the soap concentration (Table 1). The plots (Fig 1) of density (*d*) against the soap con-

TABLE 1—DENSITY AND VISCOSITY OF URANYL CAPRYLATE AND CAPRATE IN DMF AT 40±0.05°

<i>C</i> g mol dm ⁻³	<i>d</i> g ml ⁻¹	<i>d</i> - <i>d</i> ₀ / <i>C</i>	<i>η</i> c.p.	<i>η</i> _{sp}	<i>η</i> _{sp} / <i>C</i>	<i>η</i> _{sp} / <i>C</i> ^{1/2}	(<i>η</i> / <i>η</i> ₀) ²	1/log <i>η</i> / <i>η</i> ₀
Uranyl caprylate								
0.01	0.939 8	0.010	0.647 6	0.008 7	0.370	0.087 0	1.007	620.16
0.02	0.942 4	0.160	0.653 0	0.012 1	0.605	0.085 6	1.024	191.61
0.03	0.944 9	0.190	0.657 9	0.019 7	0.657	0.113 7	1.040	118.13
0.04	0.946 4	0.178	0.662 1	0.026 2	0.655	0.131 0	1.053	89.05
0.05	0.948 0	0.176	0.669 8	0.038 1	0.762	0.170 4	1.078	61.54
0.06	0.952 5	0.222	0.676 3	0.048 2	0.808	0.196 8	1.099	48.91
0.07	0.955 0	0.226	0.681 3	0.056 0	0.800	0.211 6	1.115	42.29
0.08	0.955 9	0.209	0.691 8	0.072 2	0.902	0.255 3	1.150	33.02
0.09	0.959 4	0.224	0.704 2	0.091 4	1.016	0.304 7	1.191	26.31
0.10	0.960 7	0.215	0.715 0	0.108 2	1.082	0.342 2	1.228	22.42
Uranyl caprate								
0.01	0.939 4	0.020	0.653 1	0.013 8	1.380	0.138 0	1.028	168.07
0.02	0.942 3	0.155	0.662 6	0.027 0	1.350	0.190 9	1.055	86.52
0.03	0.944 9	0.190	0.670 9	0.039 8	1.325	0.239 8	1.081	59.95
0.04	0.946 8	0.190	0.682 0	0.057 0	1.425	0.285 0	1.117	41.61
0.05	0.950 9	0.234	0.691 4	0.071 6	1.432	0.320 2	1.148	33.29
0.06	0.954 0	0.247	0.700 2	0.085 2	1.420	0.347 9	1.178	28.14
0.07	0.954 8	0.223	0.713 9	0.106 5	1.521	0.402 5	1.224	22.75
0.08	0.955 7	0.206	0.727 7	0.127 9	1.599	0.452 3	1.272	19.13
0.09	0.956 4	0.196	0.741 4	0.149 1	1.657	0.473 0	1.320	16.56
0.10	0.957 1	0.179	0.756 1	0.171 9	1.719	0.543 6	1.370	14.51

Fig. 1. Plots of density vs concentration: (○) uranyl caprylate, and (●) uranyl caprate.

centration (C , g mol dm^{-3}) are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite soap concentration (0.07 and 0.06 M) which correspond to the critical micelle concentration (CMC) of the uranyl caprylate and caprate soaps, respectively. The results show that there is a sudden change in the aggregation of the soap molecules at the CMC. The plots of the density against the soap concentration below the CMC have been extrapolated to zero soap concentration and the extrapolated values of the density, d_0 , (caprylate, 0.9370; caprate, 0.9364 g ml^{-1}) are in agreement with the experimental value 0.9392 g ml^{-1} of the density of the solvent.

The density results have been explained in terms of Root's equation,

$$d = d_0 + AC - BC^{3/2}$$

where, C is the concentration of the soaps (g mol dm^{-3}), d and d_0 are the densities of the soap solution and solvent, respectively, and the constants A and B refer to the solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions, respectively. The values of the constants A (0.082 and 0.020) and B (-0.56 and -0.92) have been obtained from the intercept, and slope of the plots of $(d - d_0)/C$ vs $C^{1/2}$ below the CMC for caprylate and caprate soaps, respectively. The results confirm that the solute-solvent interaction is larger than the solute-solute interaction in

dilute soap solutions. It is, therefore, concluded that the soap molecules do not show appreciable aggregation below the CMC and there is a marked increase in the aggregation of the soap molecules at this definite soap concentration.

Viscosity: The viscosity (η) and specific viscosity (η_{sp}) of the uranyl soaps in DMF increase with the increase in the soap concentration as well as with the chainlength of the soap (Table 1) which may be due to the increasing tendency of the soap to form aggregates with the increase in the soap concentration and the chainlength of the soap. The plots of the viscosity against the soap concentration (Fig. 2) are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite soap concentration which correspond to the CMC of uranyl caprylate (0.07 M)

Fig. 2. Plots of viscosity vs concentration: (○) uranyl caprylate, and (●) uranyl caprate.

and caprate (0.06 M), respectively. The results show that the values of the CMC vary with the chainlength of the anion in the soap molecule. The decrease in the CMC with the length of hydrocarbon chain may be due to the increase in the stability of the micelles as well as due to the increase in the tendency of aggregation. The extrapolated values of the viscosity (η_0 ; caprylate, 0.6425; caprate, 0.6450 cp) are in agreement with the experimental value of the viscosity of the solvent (0.6452 cp). The values of the intrinsic viscosity, $[\eta]$, for uranyl soaps (caprylate, 0.525; caprate, 1.315) increase with increasing chainlength of the soap. The

viscosity results are satisfactorily explained on the basis of following equations,

$$\text{Einstein}^8 : \eta_{sp} = 2.5 \bar{V} C$$

$$\text{Vand}^9 : 1/C = \left[\frac{0.921}{\bar{V}} \right]^{-1} \frac{1}{\log(\eta/\eta_0)} + \phi \bar{V}$$

$$\text{Moulik}^{10} : (\eta/\eta_0)^2 = M + K' C^2$$

$$\text{Jones - Dole}^{11} : (\eta_{sp}/C^{1/2}) = A + BC^{1/2}$$

where, \bar{V} , C , ϕ , η , η_0 and η_{sp} are the molar volume of the soap ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), concentration of the soap (g mol dm^{-3}), interaction coefficient, viscosity of the solution, viscosity of the solvent and specific viscosity, respectively, M and K' are Moulik's constants. The constants A and B of Jones - Dole's equation refer to the soap - soap and soap - solvent interactions, respectively. The plots of specific viscosity (η_{sp}) against the soap concentration (C) are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite soap concentration which corresponds to the CMC of uranyl soaps (caprylate, $0.07 M$; caprate, $0.06 M$). The plots with intercept almost equal to zero are linear below the CMC, which shows that the equation proposed by Einstein is applicable to dilute solutions of these soaps. The values of molar volume of uranyl soaps, \bar{V} , calculated from the slope of the Einstein's plots are $0.30 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ and $0.56 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for uranyl caprylate and caprate, respectively.

The plots $1/C$ vs $1/\log(\eta/\eta_0)$ are linear, which indicates that Vand's equation is applicable to these soap solutions. The values of molar volume (\bar{V} ; caprylate, 0.24 ; caprate, $0.51 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) calculated from the slope of the Vand's plots are in agreement with the values (caprylate, 0.30 ; caprate, $0.56 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) obtained from Einstein's plots. The values of interaction coefficient, ϕ , obtained from the intercept of Vand's plots for caprylate and caprate are 4.6 and 1.5 , respectively. The plots $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ vs C^2 are almost linear, which indicates that Moulik's equation is applicable to the solutions of uranyl soaps in DMF. The values of constants M and K' calculated from the intercept and slope by the plots

are 1.02 and 21 for caprylate and 1.07 and 31 for caprate, respectively.

The applicability of Jones - Dole's equation was checked by the plots of $\eta_{sp}/C^{1/2}$ vs $C^{1/2}$ which are linear below the CMC (caprylate, $0.07 M$; caprate, $0.06 M$). The values of coefficients A and B calculated from the intercept and slope of the plots below the CMC are 0.06 and 1.086 for uranyl caprylate whereas zero and 1.375 for uranyl caprate. The values of coefficient B (soap - solvent interaction) are larger than the values of coefficient A (soap - soap interaction), which confirms that the molecules of the soap do not aggregate appreciably below the CMC and there is sudden change in the aggregation above the CMC.

It is, therefore, concluded that the equations of Einstein, Vand, Moulik and Jones - Dole are applicable to dilute solutions of uranyl soaps in DMF. The values of the CMC and molar volume of these soaps calculated from these equations are in close agreement.

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